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Methods and tools to address GHG emissions in the early design stage of building renovations: A state-of-the-art review

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Abstract: This paper presents a literature review of methods and tools applied in early design stages to address greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in renovation projects. The aim is to identify focus areas in existing research and to find potential research gaps. In the literature review, 21 papers were analysed and categorised according to four different themes. The results revealed a large difference in the choice of system boundaries within the literature, making comparison of reported emissions not comparable. Most case studies address residential buildings within the European context. There is a need for more research on GHG emissions related to the renovation of different building typologies in different locations. The article highlights the need for more standardised methods for calculating GHG emissions in early design stages, allowing for comparable results and better-informed decisions for building designers.

1. Introduction

The European building industry accounts for 36% of the total European carbon dioxide emissions, and in 2022, it stood for 37% of waste generation in Europe [1]. An ageing building stock needs to be renovated and made more energy efficient, and its existing materials must be used more purposefully. Mapping of the European building stock shows that about 50% of the buildings were built before 1950 and 90% before 1990 [2]. Coupling this with current estimations that 85-95% of existing buildings will be in use in 2050 [2], it becomes apparent that to decarbonise the building industry by 2050, we must re-use and transform our existing buildings sustainably. Building designers need tools and methods to inform the building design process to achieve this.

1.1. Level of intervention and building typology

Different terminologies related to the level of intervention done to existing buildings are used. The term 'refurbishment' is often used at the lower level of intervention, and at the highest level of intervention, the terms 'adaptation' or 'transformation' are most commonly used. The different levels of interventions will have different impacts on the embodied and operational emissions when accounting for the life cycle of a building. Furthermore, the same type of intervention on different building types will have varying outcomes in terms of emissions. It is, therefore, vital that research on sustainable interventions on buildings must cover a spectrum of different building typologies and different levels of interventions. For clarity, this article will use the word 'renovation' when referring to all different levels of

interventions. The only exception will be in chapter 3.1 when referring to the terminology applied by the analysed articles.

1.2. The paradox of the calculation of emissions and early design

The early design stage is characterised by its high degree of design freedom (see Figure 1). This is where building designers have the best chance to impact the outcome of the building, but this is also where the process is non-linear, non-standardized and highly iterative [3]. In the early project phases, the lack of data and information about the building design makes informed decisions based on the potential greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions challenging[4].

Figure 1. Influence of design decision on environmental impacts.
Adapted from [5]

At the other end of the design timeline, in the late stage, there is a lot of available data about the building. Yet, this is also where designers have the least freedom to make impactful changes to the design. In this stage, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is, for example, a functional tool to establish benchmarks, but its suitability to inform the design is relatively low. On the one hand, building designers want to know which potential design would be most sustainable. Still, on the other hand, sustainability consultants need data about the design as a basis for calculations. This represents a situation where the need for information and the possibility to influence design are antithetical. To better understand this challenge, there has been an increase in published peer-reviewed articles that look at the challenge of introducing LCA or other sustainability tools early in the design process [5], [6]. However, this research has mainly focused on new buildings and, to a lesser degree, on renovating existing buildings. This begs the question of what kind of studies have been done on calculating emissions in the early design phases of building renovation. In this paper, we report the results of a study of existing research literature to find the methods and tools applied or developed to address GHG emissions in the early design stage of renovation projects.

1.3. Research question

The objective of our study was to map the existing research that has focused on addressing the impact of GHG emissions in the early design stage of the renovation process. The aim was to identify focus areas in the existing research and to find potential research gaps. The following research question was formulated to achieve this goal:

What methods and tools have been used to address GHG emissions in the early design stages of a renovation process, and how have they been applied?

This study aims to reveal strategies, tools or methods that may potentially be useful in practice, i.e., in the design of building renovation projects. We have therefore chosen to focus on articles that utilise case studies, meaning studies that refer to actual building cases or models of buildings.

2. Methodology

To answer the research question, a literature study was performed to find relevant peer-reviewed publications. An overview of the search terms and review process is presented in Figure 2.

2.1. Article Identification & inclusion in the review

To start, a set of keywords was defined, and the initial search was done in the electronic database Scopus within the search fields “Article Title, Abstract and Keywords” for the last ten years. The number of identified and selected articles depends on the chosen search terms, the database, and the author's judgement. Relevant articles that do not use the search terms in the title, keywords, or abstract will not

Figure 2. Overview of the literature search and screening process. Chapter 2.1 explains the screening criteria in more detail.

be identified in the search. This also means that, for example, information from public authorities, institutions, and research projects that are not published in peer-reviewed channels will not be included.

After removing duplicate elements identified in the literature search, the identified elements were screened manually. An essential criterion in the selection process was that the articles included a calculation of greenhouse gas emissions at some level. A part of the screening process was also to make sure that the methods presented in the studies were applied to a case study. Papers that had specifically studied historical buildings were not included in the analysis.

Most of the identified articles included some level of intervention to make the building more energy efficient. Even though there is a strong correlation between energy efficiency and operational emissions from a building, the articles that did not include any emissions calculations were excluded from the analysis. Also, the review focused on articles including significant physical interventions done to buildings. Thus, articles with topics like facility management and change in user behaviour or user adaptation were excluded from the analysis. Papers that focused on energy distribution or delivered energy to the buildings or a district were also excluded from the analysis.

2.2. Analysis and categorisation of included literature

After the initial screening, the included articles were analysed to find their main thematic focus area. The following four categories were identified in the analysis:

1. **Modelling, Data collection or BIM integration:** This category includes articles that focus on either collecting data to make a model of the buildings or integrating software or databases into the Building Information Model (BIM).
2. **Materials:** Studies that mostly focus on the emissions connected to materials used in the renovation.
3. **Optimization & Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA):** Studies in which the calculation of emissions is part of a larger multi-criteria assessment or when a type of optimization method has been applied.
4. **Other:** Included papers that do not fall under any of the previous categories and had too few similar articles with the same thematic focus for a new category to be made. For example, studies focusing on economic aspects, studies using sensitivity analysis to find the most influential parameters in the model, or studies mainly focused on examining case studies.

In addition to categorising the articles into the above-described focus areas, the articles were thoroughly analysed. The most important part of the analysis was investigating the approach to calculating GHG emissions. Therefore, special attention was given to the type of methodology applied, the referenced Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) database or standard, which software was used, which life cycle phases (system boundaries) were included, and if operational and embodied emissions were included in the calculation. As mentioned in Chapter 1.3, it was most interesting to find methods that have a higher chance of being usable in practice. Therefore, the case studies described in the publications were mapped against building typology and the location for the study.

3. Results

In this chapter, the results from the literature review and analysis are presented. Several articles have overlapping thematic approaches that could place them in more than one of the selected categories. However, it was decided to place each article in the category that was found to fit most closely. The analysis focuses on determining the focus areas and the gaps in the literature. First, a summary of the analysed literature is given in Chapter 3.1, with a focus on the chosen methods and tools. Then, in Chapter 3.2, the analysis of GHG emissions, case studies and building types is presented. Figure 3 shows an overview of the data collected in the analysis and presents data regarding the approaches to calculating GHG emissions and the chosen case study.

3.1. Strategies identified and reviewed

This subchapter presents a summary of all the analysed papers according to the categories described in Chapter 2.2.

3.1.1. Modelling, Data Collection or BIM-integration

The category contains 3 articles. Selimovic et al. [7] utilised a scanning technology to produce a surface model derived from a point cloud to assess facade renovation measures. The authors then did an LCA based on the gathered data in order to check the environmental potential of changing outer windows in a façade retrofit.

Soust-Verdaguer et al. [8] used a BIM plug-in that helped simplify the LCSA (environmental, economic, social) calculations when assessing the renovation of the building envelope. The results show the aggregated embodied emissions divided into the life cycle stages [A1-A3, A5], [B2, B3, B4] and [C1], according to EN 15978:2011.

Göswein et al. [9] presented the CirBIM database tool that connects the BIM model to a database containing circularity indicators based on an adaptation for buildings of the Material Circularity Indicators (MCI) by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation. The tools are applied to a case study building, including the CO₂eq for the outflows (recovered, demolished) and inflows (reused and new material). No specific EPD database is mentioned in the study, but the authors state they chose EPDs based on EN 15804:2012 + A2:2019 because of the inclusion of Module C and Module D in that specific standard.

3.1.2. Materials

There are 3 articles that mostly focus on the emissions connected to materials in renovation. Gaspar & Santos [10] focused only on embodied emissions when studying three different renovation and demolition scenarios for a single-family home in southern Europe. The scenarios were (1) the original construction, (2) the demolition of the original construction and the building of a new house, and (3) the partial demolition of the original construction and a major refurbishment operation.

Mazzoli et al. [11] proposed a methodology (EASY) that combines circularity criteria with LCA, embodied energy and embodied carbon (author's terminology), and Life Cycle Cost (LCC). The study uses the software "One-click LCA" to calculate emissions and provides results to compare to the emissions provided by the EASY methodology.

Passoni et al. [12] applied Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) principles in the early design stages to assess the environmental impact of seismic retrofitting of four different alternatives. The authors gave special attention to phases B3, B4 and B5 and included a hazard risk in these phases of the use phase.

3.1.3. Optimization & Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA)

In several of the articles, the environmental assessment is part of a larger pool of multi-criteria assessments or as a part of optimisation-calculation. Shahi et al. [13] used various physics-based simulation tools to simulate eight different parameters for ten different renovation strategies on a BIM model. For the LCA calculations and energy use, they used the software Tally and Sefaira, respectively. Multi-attribute utility (MAU) is the selected Multi-Criteria Decision Method (MCDM) for this paper to determine the design strategies that perform well for most considered measures.

Aguacil & Rey [14] investigated a multi-family residential building using four different renovation scenarios simulated with the software Design-builder, where LCA was one of four groups of indicators for the assessment.

Aruta et al. [15] simulated different renovation scenarios for a large-scale district approach (29 buildings) compared to individual buildings to assess the potential benefits in terms of energy savings and related emissions.

Luo [16] utilised particle swarm optimisation (PSO) algorithms to assess optimal passive and active retrofit interventions. This was done by two iterative processes of having two different optimisation sets. The first optimisation aimed to minimise the whole-life carbon emission (gate-to-grave) of the building,

including embodied and operational emissions. The second set of optimisations aimed at making the operation of the building as effective as possible.

Ostermeyer et al. [17] presented a multidimensional Pareto optimisation based on LCC, LCA, and social assessment to evaluate optimal refurbishments for residential buildings. The ecological indicators used in the LCA as part of the optimisation were based on ReCipe H/A, IPCC 100, and Cumulative Energy indicator (CED). The results of the ecological assessment were given as a percentage between 0 and 100%.

Romani et al. [18] used multicriteria analysis (Weight sum, min-max and Pareto) and metamodeling to analyse the optimal refurbishment scenarios for a residential building. The environmental assessments are based on twelve indicators given in the French environmental and health reference data for buildings, INIES 2020. As Romani et al. problematise in their study, their chosen database for products (NF EN 15804+A1 French standard) presents the emissions data only as a total of “Cradle-to-grave”, not allowing for distinction between the stages in the life cycle of the study product.

Schwartz et al. [19] applied multi-objective generic algorithms (MOGA) to assess life cycle carbon footprints (LCCF) and LCC to optimise different refurbishment options. The method was then applied to a case study focusing on refurbishing the building envelope. The embodied and operational emissions are shown as total and not split into different life-cycle phases.

3.1.4. Other

The 8 studies included in this category addressed a range of different aspects. Olsson et al. [20] presented the BECEREN tool that can calculate energy use, potential climate change due to energy use and embodied materials, and LCC in the early project stage. The calculations are based on general data on materials, emissions, GWP and cost, and predefined options for technical systems.

Marini et al. [21] showed an approach to combine the analysis of seismic retrofit and energy refurbishment of buildings. This is to attain a more holistic view of the embodied emissions and operational carbon that come with refurbishing buildings that need structural upgrades.

Huuhka et al. [22] adopted a consequential replacement framework (CRF) that has been used in the car industry to do a Life cycle assessment on a school building from the 1950s. This was done to assess the impact of three different renovation scenarios that span from the demolition and construction of a new building to a comprehensive refurbishment. The study used the Finnish national method (“MoE method”) to perform a whole-life carbon assessment.

Tsay et al. [23] used the life-cycle CO₂ (LCCO₂) emissions and annual energy consumption from 744 different building envelope renovation projects to develop a machine-learning model. The goal of making the machine-learning model was to predict the life-cycle carbon footprint and annual energy consumption for a typical row house in Taiwan.

Rodrigues and Freire [24] presented a streamlined LCC and environmental assessment method to do a sensitivity analysis for different retrofit scenarios for different building typologies and occupancy composition and behaviour. The authors utilise sensitivity analysis to find the key drivers for emissions and costs. To address uncertainty, the authors utilised Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) to identify decision variables and calculate impact predictions.

Galimshina et al. [25] modelled uncertain parameters and performed a sensitivity analysis to find the most influential parameters for selecting renovation measures. They then used uncertainty quantification (Sobol’s indices) to identify sources of uncertainty and how the model was influenced by them.

Silva et al. [26] presented three different renovation scenarios: Zero Energy Building (ZEB), nearly Zero Energy Building (nZEB) and basic renovation for a multifamily building in Portugal. The study has a special focus on the contribution of solar systems to the nZEB and ZEB design concepts for renovation.

Sundling et al. [27] used four different renovation concepts and compared the life cycle profit analysis and life cycle impact assessment. The different renovation concepts were (1) minimalist, (2) code-compliant, (3) low-energy and (4) low-energy plus concepts, including the vertical extension of

the building. The LCA results included Global warming potential, Cumulative energy demand and Non-renewable energy.

3.2. Analysis of GHG emission, case studies and building types

In this subchapter, an overview and explanation of the analysis described in chapter 2.2 will be given. The analysis overview is presented in Figure 3, and it is split into two parts. Part one shows the analysis of how the calculations are handled in the studied papers, and part two, “Case study”, shows the building typology and location of the case study used in the analysed papers.

3.2.1. Analysis – emissions

In this subchapter, the “Emissions” part of the analysed articles will be presented. Nine columns summarise the findings on how the papers have handled emissions. The ID number corresponds with the numbering in the list of references.

Category	ID	Analysis - Emissions							Case study		
		Software	EPD Database	Emission factor - E	Reference Standard	Embodied	Operational	Lifetime	Life cycle stages	Building typology	Country
Modeling/ Data Collection/ BIM	[7]	CAALA	-	-	-	●	●	50	A1-A3, B6	Residential, multi	-
	[8]	Novel	●	-	●	●	-	-	A1-A3,A5, B2-B4, C1	Residential, multi	ES
	[9]	Novel	●	-	-	●	-	-	A1-A3	Residential, single	PT
Materials	[10]	-	-	-	-	●	●	50	A1-A3, B6, C1-C4	Residential, single	PT
	[11]	OneClick LCA	-	-	-	●	-	-	A1-A3	Residential, single	IT
	[12]	-	●	-	●	●	-	-	A1-A3, C3-C4, D	Residential, multi	IT
Optimization & MCA	[13]	Tally	-	-	-	●	●	-	Total Life cycle	Residential, multi	CA
	[14]	-	-	●	-	●	●	-	-	Residential, multi	CH
	[15]	-	-	●	-	-	●	-	B6	Residential, multi	FR
	[16]	-	-	-	●	●	●	60	Total Life cycle	Office Building	UK
	[17]	-	●	-	●	●	-	30	-	Residential, multi	FR, SE, NL
	[18]	-	●	-	-	●	●	50	Total Life cycle	Residential, multi	FR
Other	[19]	Novel	●	●	●	●	●	60	Total Life cycle	Residential, multi	TW
	[20]	Novel	●	-	●	●	●	50	A1-B5	Residential, multi	SE
	[21]	-	-	-	▣	●	●	-	-	Residential, multi	IT
	[22]	OneClick LCA	-	-	●	●	●	50	Total Life cycle	School	FI
	[23]	SimaPro	●	-	-	●	●	30	-	Residential, single	TW
	[24]	-	-	-	▣	●	●	50	Total Life cycle	Residential	South-Europe
	[25]	-	●	-	●	●	-	60	A1-A3, B4, B6, C1-C4	Commercial + Resi, m	CH
	[26]	SimaPro	●	-	●	●	●	30	A1-A5, B2-B6, C2-C4	Residential, multi	PT
[27]	Eco-Bat	-	-	-	●	●	-	-	Residential, multi	SE	

Figure 3 An overview of the analysed papers. The ID corresponds with the references in Chapter 3.1. The black dot (●) indicates either the inclusion of embodied or operational emissions or the disclosure of used standards, the EPD database, and the energy emission factor. For further explanation, see Chapter 3.2.1.

The Column “Software” refers to what, if any, software is used to perform emissions calculations. The notation “Novel” was applied if the study had developed its software to perform these calculations. In the second column, “EPD Database”, a fully covered black dot means that the study disclosed which EPD database applied, or which standards were used to produce the EPDs. If the study disclosed the utilised software but not the chosen EPD database or standard, the study is marked with a rhombus sign in the “EPD Database”-column. The same logic is applied to the next column, “Emission factor- E” (E

used as an abbreviation for energy in this context). Here, it is indicated if the studies have disclosed the chosen emission factor for energy.

“Reference standard” refers to whether the study has disclosed which standard has been used to calculate the emissions. The square symbols have been used when the studies have referred to a secondary study for their methodological approach. In the column “Lifetime”, one can find the chosen period of study in the given articles.

In the two next columns, “Embodied” and “Operational”, a black dot is given if it is made clear what type of emissions are calculated. In the column “Life cycle stages”, there is an overview of the included life-cycle phases in the studies. System stages are defined based on the definition of system boundaries given in EN 15978:2011[28]. When the notation “Total Life cycle” is used in Figure 3, it is a collective term chosen if the articles have disclosed either “whole life cycle” or “total life cycle” as a boundary condition for the study. It is important to highlight that the findings in “Embodied”, “Operational”, and “Life cycle stage” only show what kind of input data the analysed articles have included in their calculation of emissions and not how the resulting emissions are presented in the respective articles. For almost all the studied papers, with very few exceptions, aggregated results for the calculated emissions are reported.

3.2.2. Case studies

The second part of the table shows the building typology and location of the case studies included in the articles. The notation “Residential, multi” has been used as a collective term to describe when the articles include anything larger than single-family housing, which has been given the notation “Residential, single”. In nineteen out of twenty-one cases, some kind of residential buildings have been used as a case study.

4. Discussion

The objective of this study was to map existing research that has focused on addressing the impact of GHG emissions in the early design of the renovation process, and the following research question was chosen; “*What methods and tools have been used to address GHG emissions in the early design stages of a renovation process, and how have they been applied?*”

As shown in the first part of this literature review, there is a diversity of topics in the scientific literature addressing GHG emissions in the early design of renovation projects. The articles show a wide range of methodical approaches for how the emissions are calculated and how the assessment or optimisation is performed. Therefore, making any direct comparison of results or outcomes is not feasible.

The study has also shown that there are large differences when it comes to the choice of system boundaries in the studies, which applies to the choice of building or component lifetime, the inclusion of life-cycle stages, the use of software, and the inclusion of embodied and operational emissions. This is a significant obstacle when comparing results from different studies, something that is a known problem in the LCA community [29].

As mentioned in chapter 1.4, the aim is to identify potential research gaps for future research possibilities. Whilst most of the studies have included both operational and embodied emissions in their calculations, there is a lack of studies that separate the emissions into the different life cycle stages when reporting the calculated emissions. In most cases, only aggregated results are presented. This might be a consequence of trying to perform calculations of emissions early in the design phase, where data availability and quality are a problem. However, a more detailed result would potentially allow for a better understanding of the consequences of emissions for different renovation interventions and, therefore, be more useful for building designers.

The review has shown that most of the studies focus on residential buildings in different forms, e.g. single-family, apartment buildings or multi-family housing, whilst only three articles focus on other building types, like offices or multi-use. As highlighted in the introduction, the same kind of intervention on different building types will have varying outcomes in terms of emissions. Therefore, research on a

larger range of building typologies exposed to varying levels of intervention is needed to have a better understanding of the consequences in terms of emissions. As shown in this review, case studies from Europe, Northern America and Asia are represented in the literature. However, 17 out of 21 case studies are in Europe.

5. Conclusion & Future work

This paper presented a literature review of scientific articles focusing on methods and tools applied in early design stages to address GHG emissions in renovation projects using a reproducible search query. The main findings of the literature review can be summarised in the following way:

- All the analysed articles have chosen different systems boundaries with regard to the included life cycle phases and chosen building lifetimes. Although one could argue that the articles that chose “Total Life Cycle” and the same building lifetime have the same system boundaries, it is unclear how the studies have defined the life cycle phases and how they have been handled, e.g. life cycle phase D.
- 10 out of 21 reviewed studies disclosed the chosen database or the standard for calculating EPDs. However, some studies can be said to have indirectly disclosed it by describing the software being utilised. If this is considered, a total of 15 of the studied papers could be said to have disclosed the database or calculation standard.
- Out of the 15 studies that included operational emissions in the calculation, only three disclosed the chosen emissions factor for the supplied energy.
- 9 out of 21 reviewed studies disclosed the chosen standard or methodology for calculating the emissions, while two referenced a method found in other studies. None of the studies that referenced a standardised methodology have been developed explicitly for use in renovation.
- 19 out of 21 reviewed articles had some type of residential building as the chosen case study. This was a mix of single-family housing, multi-family housing or apartment buildings.
- A significant majority, 17 out of 21, of the case studies were in Europe.

Some limitations in this study should be highlighted. As mentioned in the introduction, in the early design, the scarcity of available data on the building design makes informed decisions based on the potential GHG emissions challenging and uncertain. Our review has briefly touched upon the topic of uncertainty regarding the disclosure of EPD databases and applied methodology. Further work should study the limitations and uncertainty when calculating emissions based on the available data one can expect to have during the early design stage of building renovations. For a deeper understanding of the chosen methods and tools, it is necessary to map out the building parts and elements included in the studies in greater detail. By investigating the available and selected data and the chosen cut-off points for the inclusion of materials, one could better understand the strengths and weaknesses regarding the applicability of the selected methods.

A next step would be to expand the work in this article to the methodological papers referred to in two of the studied papers. Also, research that was not published in peer-reviewed channels was not included in the survey. Thus, it would be beneficial to include grey literature from institutions, research projects, conferences, etc., to get a broader understanding of how the building community handles this topic. During the screening phase of the applied methodologies, several articles were excluded due to their content or, in some cases, poor quality. This process is partly based on subjective judgment, and other authors may have chosen a different subset of literature.

Considering the ongoing climate change and the need for further decarbonisation and better utilisation of the existing building stock, research on making building interventions more sustainable is expected to become even more relevant. To better assess emissions in the early stages of the design process, building designers need more standardised methods to perform the calculations. Standardised methods would potentially help make the assessments more reliable and compare findings in different studies. This would allow for better-informed design decisions that lower the GHG emission impact from the existing building stock.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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